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Research Article

**A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON THE PROPERTIES OF
ANTISICKLING AGENTS****¹Dr. Maimona Rafiq, ²Dr. Muhammad Rizwan Saeed, ³Dr. Hafiz Rana Kamran
Ijaz**¹Fatima Memorial Hospital, Lahore²Shalamar Hospital, Lahore³WAPDA Hospital Complex, Lahore**Abstract:**

Objective: The most common antisickling medicines are the chemical agents of thiocyanate, hydroxyurea & tellurite & in recent times, these are the centre of research for many research works. The AP (anti-sickling properties) of these three drugs was interrogated & contrasted with one another in this research work.

Methodology: Human abnormal or sickle blood kept alive with the help of the drugs in artificial environment outside the living organism at concentrations linked to the prescribed amount utilized by the patients in the organism or in vivo. The function of the haemoglobin & particular features of the method of sickling were calculated with the use of the standard procedures utilized in selecting the antisickling means.

Results: All these medicines prevented the sickling of abnormal blood without oxygen & the creation of the sickle cells in only one dose & in a way which is depending upon the time. The drugs of thiocyanate, hydroxyurea & tellurite prevented the process of sickling twenty mM, forty mM & fifty μ M respectively. Thiocyanate & hydroxyurea enhance the life span of the sickle RBC as displayed in the important reduction in lysis of erythrocytes with the release of haemoglobin & fragility of osmotic while tellurite has the ability to increase the various factors of the blood. The increase in the delay of the duration of polymerization of HbS (haemoglobin S) is the result of these three drugs. Thiocyanate & hydroxyurea are the cause of high value of ratio of solubility & oxygen affinity of haemoglobin S.

Conclusion: The outcome of this research work shows that these 3 mentioned drugs have the ability of antisickling in an artificial environment outside the living organism with thiocyanate as the most effective one.

Keywords: Organism, Antisickling, Solubility, Anomalies, Haemoglobin, Auto haemolysis, Potassium.

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INTRODUCTION:

The disease of sickle cells is a genetic abnormality of the blood which takes place as an outcome of the availability of the anomalous haemoglobin in the RBC of a person. It is very common & important medical abnormality of the haemoglobin with a high rate in Africa, the countries of the Middle East & among offspring of Africans living in countries of the West [1]. The anomalous HbS is very different from the normal HbA (haemoglobin A) in the 6th amino acid of beta chain where glutamic acid is replaced by the valine. This replacement put non polar remaining on the outer side of the haemoglobin S & causes the reduction in the level of solubility which results in sickling & creation of the polymer at less tension of the oxygen [2]. Some of the aspects which are the cause of medical manifestations of the disease of sickle cell are the attributors to the operational anomalies of sickle RBC which contains; low solubility & affinity with oxygen, creation of the ISC (irreversibly sickled cells), high amount of osmotic fragility and the creation of the autohaemolysis & methaemoglobin.

Some capable agents of antisickling earlier interrogated resulted haemolysis of sickle RBC at efficient amount of the dose & declared as not inappropriate for medically utilization [3]. Upper mentioned three drugs are the chemical agents which are best antisickling drugs & experienced by many research works [4]. This case study conducted to conclude the comparison of the antisickling process of these chemicals & the impacts on the parameters of RBC.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The infected blood samples were gathered from the patients who were the visitor of OPD of Haematology Department at Mayo Hospital Lahore. The willingness from patients was taken and ethical committee of the hospital gave the approval for the conduction of the study. The salts of sodium

thiocyanate & potassium tellurite were the commodities of Hopkins & Williams limited England. British Drug House is the manufacturer of the Hydroxyurea. The method of inhibition of sickling depended upon the use of microscope as elaborated by Iyamu [5]. Blood sample of about 0.1 millilitres ml blood sample was placed in the pipette of one millilitres Hemox buffer. The 0.1 millilitres forty-five mM dithionite with the adding of 0.1 millilitres sample of the drug deoxygenation was attained. This amalgam placed at three hundred and seventy centigrade for about 1 hour after which these sections were gathered in the absence of air & hastily fixed with the saline of buffer. Then it was placed on the mount of the microscope for magnified view and examined by two evaluators who calculated one hundred cells of blood to conclude the quantity of abnormal and healthy cells. Cells were normal if their shape was like a disc of biconcave while the cells with other shapes were considered as abnormal. The method of Wolf [6] was in use for the calculation of the auto haemolysis & osmotic fragility of sickle RBC. The haemoglobin S solubility ratio was calculated with the utilization of the Chang [7]. Schechter [8] method was in use for the calculation of the delay time in the polymerization of the haemoglobin S. The procedure of Benesch [9] employed for the fortitude of oxyhaemoglobin & methaemoglobin percentages. SPSS software version ten and ANOVA software were in use for the analysis of the collected data.

RESULTS:

The most favourable sickling reticence amount for sodium thiocyanate, hydroxyurea & tellurite was twenty mM, forty mM and fifty μ M respectively. These are the lowest amounts required to get the greater reticence. Figure 1 displays the sickling inhibition which is dependent on time by the three chemical agents.

Fig-1: Time-Course inhibition of sickling human sickle

Thiocyanate incubated blood had very low quantity of the sickle cells of about thirty-eight percent as compared to the tellurite as fifty percent & hydroxyurea as sixty-three percent after 2 hour of dose. Natural patient had about ninety-three percent sickle bloods at the finishing time off the incubation period. ISC decreased from twenty-eight percent to different low percentages due to impact of the antisickling agents as shown in Figure 2. Figure 3

Fig-2: Inhibition of Irreversibly Sick Cell

displays that the curve of osmotic fragility of SRBC was transferred to the left side in the availability of the tellurite while thiocyanate & hydroxyurea transferred to the right side. The impacts of these chemical agents on some RBC are displayed in Table-1. Tellurite considerably enhanced the RBC haemolysis about by 18.6% compared to thiocyanate & hydroxyurea considerably decreased it by 30.7% & 19.6% respectively.

Thiocyanate & hydroxyurea appreciably enhanced oxyhaemoglobin by one hundred and eleven percent and thirty-nine percent respectively as compared with the healthy control. Tellurite & hydroxyurea considerably stirred the production of met haemoglobin 61.5% & forty-five percent respectively as compared to the healthy controls.

Fig-3: Effect of Hydroxyurea, Tellurite and thiocyanate on osmotic fragility

Haemoglobin S solubility was considerably increased in the availability of thiocyanate about one hundred and thirty percent & hydroxyurea of about fifty-four percent as compared to the healthy control. The comparison is displayed in the Table-1.

Indices	Control		Hydroxyurea		Tellurite		Thiocyanate	
	Mean	± SD	Mean	± SD	Mean	± SD	Mean	± SD
Oxyhaemoglobin concentration (%)	24.100	±2.740 a	33.500	±2.480 b	24.000	±2.730 a	50.800	±2.600 c
Methaemoglobin concentration (%)	1.950	±0.120 a	2.830	±0.100 b	3.150	±0.130 c	1.970	±0.090 a
Degree of haemolysis (%)	6.520	± 0.100 a	5.240	± 0.130 b	7.730	± 0.180 c	4.520	± 0.120 d
HbS solubility ratio	1.000	±0.035 a	1.540	±0.058 b	1.020	±0.061 a	2.300	±0.095 c
Delay time of HbS polymerization (minute)	11.300	±1.500 a	19.400	±2.200 b	29.000	±1.800 c	24.200	±2.100 d

Values are Mean, ±SD, n=6. Values with different alphabets a, b, c and d along a row are significantly different at p<0.05.

DISCUSSION:

The anomalous structure of RBC in the condition of deoxygenated was noticeably advanced as displayed by the important decrease in the rate of sickle cell upon nurturing of these chemical agents. The reticence of this sickling was dependant on dose and time. Thiocyanate is the most effective among these three chemical agents of antisickling in vitro. Thiocyanate has the ability to react with the reacts with the valine which is remaining of haemoglobin & carbamylate [10]. The method of action of drug tellurite is thought to be by capability of swelling the RBC which leads into hydration of the cell [11]. Hydroxyurea is recommended to take action in vitro by reacting with Hb to create the nitrosyl Hb which is a modification which inhibits the sickling of the RBC [12]. The creation of the ISC (irreversibly sickled cells) has been credited to various states as complete damage to the membrane, gathering of the ions of calcium, recurring sickling & unsickling, depletion of the ATP & dehydration in some amount of the RBC [13]. The intensity of haemolysis & osmotic fragility of SRBC (sickle red blood cell) became higher in the availability of the tellurite while thiocyanate & hydroxyurea decreased these aspects of the blood. In vitro research works have displayed ions of tellurite (+4) pierce the membrane of RBC & in the availability of low glutathione create telluride (2+) which is the reason of the damage to the membrane [11]. Thiocyanate is most common due to its great prevention effect with high life span of RBC [14]. Polymerisation & sickling of haemoglobin S is

preferred with deoxygenated condition of the haemoglobin. Rodgers [15] concluded that the increase in the oxygen affinity can decrease this problem. This function can be attained by the use of many chemical compounds [16]. The proof in available that valine of amino terminal remains in the form of intermolecular bridges of salts when Hb is with the conformation of the deoxy [17]. The availability of the unaltered group of carbamyl has the ability to stabilize the conformation of oxy [18]. This disease has the ability to shorten the life of RBC and other high risks due to absence of the oxygen [19]. The calculation of the delay time is very important in the evaluation of the efficiency of the antisickling agents because it provides with the quantity of the reticence of polymerization which has the better impacts on the life of the patients [20].

CONCLUSION:

The findings of this case study showed that these 3 chemical agents are suitable agents of antisickling and prevent the sickling of the sickle RBC in vitro. Thiocyanate & hydroxyurea has the ability to increase the life span of RBC in vitro while tellurite is the main reason of the osmotic fragility of the RBC. Thiocyanate is declared as most efficient out of these three chemical agents and tellurite was second in effectiveness.

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